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Dermatological Diagnosis using EfficientNet

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Abstract— Skin disease needs proper diagnosis, but the conventional approach is usually unreliable. CNNs can be used in skin image analysis, and such datasets as ISIC 2019 make AI diagnosis more powerful. This study presents an advanced machine learning approach for skin disease classification using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), leveraging the ISIC 2019 Archive—a comprehensive dataset featuring high-resolution skin lesion images and associated metadata. The project involved extensive data preprocessing, normalization, augmentation, and Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) to address dataset imbalances and reveal key insights. A robust CNN architecture was developed to extract intricate features from skin lesion images, essential for precise classification. Additionally, a Multimodal Convolutional Network Model was proposed, integrating image data with structured patient information to enhance diagnostic accuracy. Experimental results demonstrated the model's potential for clinical application, surpassing traditional CNN performance in accuracy and reliability. This research highlights the transformative role of deep learning in dermatology and lays the groundwork for future advancements, including model optimization, refined performance metrics, and the development of a user-friendly web application to facilitate widespread adoption in healthcare settings.

Keywords— Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), ISIC 2019 Archive, Multimodal Convolutional Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases are a significant global health concern, affecting millions of individuals and posing a diagnostic challenge for healthcare professionals. Traditional diagnostic methods primarily rely on visual assessments by dermatologists, which can be subjective and prone to inaccuracies. In regions with limited access to specialized healthcare providers, these challenges are further exacerbated, leading to delays in diagnosis and treatment. This highlights the urgent need for automated, accurate, and reliable diagnostic systems to assist in identifying skin conditions.

The rapid advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), offer promising solutions for addressing these challenges. CNNs are highly effective in image recognition tasks, making them ideal for analyzing high-resolution skin lesion images. The availability of datasets such as the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) 2019 Archive has enabled the development and evaluation of AI-based systems for skin disease classification. These systems aim to improve diagnostic accuracy, enhance consistency, and reduce dependency on specialist resources.

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This study focuses on developing an advanced CNN-based classification model to accurately identify skin diseases using skin lesion images. To further enhance performance, a Multimodal Convolutional Network was introduced, incorporating structured patient data alongside image inputs. The project included comprehensive data preprocessing, augmentation, and Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) to address data imbalances and extract valuable insights. The proposed system demonstrates the potential of AI-driven diagnostics in dermatology, offering a practical and scalable solution for clinical use.

The objective of this research is to design a robust CNN model capable of analyzing skin lesion images while integrating multimodal data to improve classification accuracy. By evaluating the model's effectiveness using performance metrics and real-world datasets, this study aims to demonstrate the practicality of AI in dermatological diagnostics. The scope encompasses data preparation, model development, and validation, focusing on enhancing diagnostic accuracy and reliability. Ultimately, this work bridges the gap between technology and healthcare, laying the groundwork for future innovations such as user-friendly applications that can democratize access to reliable skin disease diagnostics.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Skin [1] disease detection is crucial in medical diagnosis, and timely identification is essential. This work implements a skin disease detection system using image preprocessing and machine learning techniques. The proposed method employs image resizing and enhancement, followed by feature selection from three color models (RGB, HSI, and LAB) and histogram count. Ten features are selected from the color models and histogram count, which are then used to train Decision Tree (DT) and Support Vector Machine (SVM)-based algorithms.

The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method achieves better accuracy with the enhancement of the dataset. The SVM-based algorithm outperforms the DT-based algorithm, with an overall accuracy improvement of 6% with enhancement, compared to without enhancement. The detection accuracy is improved to 3% with the enhancement using DT, and 6% with the enhancement using SVM. The findings suggest that the proposed method can effectively detect skin diseases, and the enhancement of the dataset plays a crucial role in improving the accuracy of the machine learning algorithms.

Machine learning models, particularly Support Vector Machines (SVMs), have been widely explored in medical image analysis due to their ability to classify various conditions with high accuracy. A study analysing six datasets, each consisting of 500 images spanning five distinct skin diseases, demonstrated significant performance variations based on dataset composition. While some datasets, such as those containing Atopic Eczema, Candidiasis, Melanoma, and Herpes, achieved nearly 99% validation accuracy, others showed training accuracy as low as 10%. Despite strong training performance, testing accuracy varied between 75% and 85%, with error rates ranging from 15% to 25%. This highlights the sensitivity of SVM models to dataset composition and the need for robust generalization techniques. Furthermore, scalability tests revealed that while SVMs maintained high accuracy on a 2000-image dataset, accuracy dropped to 84% when extended to 3000 images. These findings emphasize the importance of optimizing SVM classifiers for large-scale medical image datasets [2].

Deep learning techniques [3], particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have gained prominence in medical image analysis. One major challenge associated with deep CNNs is the insufficiency of high-quality training data. Unlike natural image datasets such as ImageNet, which contains millions of labelled samples, medical image datasets are often limited, restricting the effective utilization of deep networks. Studies indicate that CNNs face performance degradation when exceeding 100 layers due to data constraints. Another challenge is weight-sharing between segmentation and classification networks. Research suggests that segmentation and classification require different feature representations, as segmentation is performed at the original image scale, while classification involves resized patches. Although both networks may use pre-trained weights from ImageNet, sharing weights completely may not be beneficial. Recent advancements propose integrating probabilistic graphical models, such as Bayesian learning, to improve CNN generalization in medical image analysis. By enhancing the discrimination capability of very deep CNNs, researchers aim to mitigate training data limitations and improve classification performance.

Comparative [4] performance analysis of CNN architectures, including Inception-v3, DenseNet-201, and ResNet-50, reveals key insights into medical image classification. Experimental studies show that ResNet-50 outperforms both Inception-v3 and DenseNet-201 in sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and F1-score.

Specifically, ResNet-50 achieved an accuracy of 81.57%, compared to 81.29% for Inception-v3 and 73.44% for DenseNet-201. Confusion matrix analysis further demonstrates that ResNet-50 effectively classifies benign, seborrheic keratosis, and melanoma cases with improved precision. Additionally, integrating segmentation techniques with classification models enhances feature extraction, improving diagnostic performance. Future research could focus on validating these models in clinical settings to assess real-world applicability. Moreover, incorporating handcrafted clinical features alongside deep learning-based representations may further enhance recognition accuracy in medical diagnostics.

A study also investigated the impact of dataset augmentation in CNN-based medical image classification. The dataset, initially comprising 170 images, was expanded to 6120 original and synthesized images using augmentation techniques such as cropping, scaling, and rotation. The dataset was split using an 80%-20% training-to-testing ratio. Results showed that deep learning frameworks effectively enhance classification accuracy when trained on augmented datasets. Furthermore, comparative analysis with prior methods demonstrated that CNN-based classification surpasses traditional approaches in sensitivity, specificity, and overall accuracy. However, false positives and false negatives remain a challenge, highlighting the necessity for further optimization in deep learning-based diagnostic systems. Future research could focus on validating these models in clinical settings to assess real-world applicability. Moreover, incorporating handcrafted clinical features alongside deep learning-based representations may further enhance recognition accuracy in medical diagnostics [5].

Deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have significantly advanced medical image recognition, largely influenced by the success of large-scale natural image datasets like ImageNet. However, medical imaging datasets remain limited, making training from scratch a challenge. Research suggests three major approaches for CNN-based medical image classification: (1) training from scratch, (2) using off-the-shelf pre-trained CNN features, and (3) employing unsupervised CNN pre-training with supervised fine-tuning.

A key method, transfer learning, has been proven effective for adapting CNNs pre-trained on natural image datasets to medical tasks. This approach has been particularly useful in two key applications: thoraco-abdominal lymph node (LN) detection and interstitial lung disease (ILD) classification. Experimental results demonstrate that CNN-based detection systems can achieve state-of-the-art performance, with an 85% sensitivity at 3 false positives per patient for mediastinal LN detection. Additionally, the first five-fold cross-validation classification results have been reported for ILD classification.

One major bottleneck in CNN-based medical image analysis is the availability of well-annotated datasets. Unlike computer vision applications that have benefited from progressively growing datasets like Scene-15, MIT Indoor-67, and SUN-397, medical image classification still struggles with data scarcity. To mitigate this, CNN-based transfer learning and dataset augmentation techniques are being explored to improve diagnostic accuracy[6]

III. PROPOSED MODEL

The project commenced with the acquisition of a comprehensive dataset from the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) 2019 Archive via Kaggle. This dataset, a cornerstone of our project, includes a wide range of images representing various skin diseases, accompanied by relevant metadata. Our initial efforts focused on preprocessing this dataset, including handling missing values and structuring the data for efficient analysis. A significant portion of our work involved Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), where we utilized various visualization tools to gain insights into the dataset. This process revealed crucial aspects such as the distribution of histological types, age distribution, and anatomical location of skin diseases, thereby guiding our model development strategy.

1) *System Framework*

The proposed system for skin disease classification is a deep learning-based pipeline designed to provide an automated dermatological diagnosis. The system follows a modular API-based architecture, ensuring seamless interaction between various components. The key elements of this framework include the user interface (UI), application programming interface (API), preprocessing module and convolutional neural network (CNN) model. These components collectively enable efficient image processing, feature extraction, classification, and result presentation to the user.

2) *Input Image and preprocessing*

The classification process begins with the user uploading an image of a skin lesion through the UI. Once the image is uploaded, the API receives the request and sends it to the preprocessing module for standardization. The preprocessing phase is crucial to ensure that images maintain a uniform structure. It involves resizing the image to a fixed dimension to match the input requirements of the CNN model. Additionally, normalization is applied to scale pixel values between 0 and 1, which helps improve the model's learning efficiency.

3) *Feature extraction using deep learning*

Following preprocessing, the image is passed to the CNN model for feature extraction and classification. The

proposed system leverages EfficientNet, a state-of-the-art deep learning architecture known for its superior balance between computational efficiency and classification accuracy. EfficientNet employs a compound scaling approach to optimize depth, width, and resolution, allowing it to extract hierarchical features from skin lesion images. Through multiple convolutional layers, the model captures both low-level and high-level patterns, distinguishing between various dermatological conditions with high precision. The extracted features are then processed through fully connected layers to generate a final classification output, predicting the most likely disease category.

4) Classification and Display of Results

Once the pre-processed image is passed through the CNN model, the system generates a prediction output representing the probability of different skin disease categories. The classification results are then transmitted back to the UI via the API, where the user can view the predicted disease category. The modular architecture ensures scalability and flexibility, allowing for future enhancements such as metadata inclusion, multimodal learning (integrating patient demographics with image data), and explainability mechanisms to improve interpretability. The proposed system is designed to facilitate fast and reliable dermatological diagnosis, providing an efficient and accurate tool for skin disease classification.

Fig 1: Sequence Diagram of Proposed Model

Once preprocessed, the image is classified by a CNN model (EfficientNet), which loads the pre-trained weights and predicts the probability of different skin disease categories. The classification results are returned via the API and displayed on the Gradio UI, allowing users to interpret the diagnosis instantly. This interactive UI ensures a seamless experience while maintaining scalability and efficiency for real-time dermatological assessments

A. Methodology

The methodology on how to implement the solution within the proposed solution is thus structured as follows:

1) *Data acquisition*: The dataset used in this study was obtained from the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) 2019 Archive, which provides a vast collection of labelled skin lesion images. To streamline the integration process, the dataset was acquired using the Kaggle API, enabling automated and efficient retrieval. This dataset includes images belonging to multiple skin disease categories, making it highly suitable for deep learning-based classification tasks.

2) *Data preprocessing*: To improve model performance and enhance data quality, extensive preprocessing steps were undertaken. Initially, the dataset was inspected and cleaned to identify and remove any corrupted or irrelevant images that might negatively impact model training. Handling missing values was also a crucial step, where incomplete metadata was either imputed or excluded based on its significance

3) *Machine learning model selection*: The core classification model employed in this study is based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), specifically EfficientNet, which has demonstrated superior performance in medical image classification tasks. EfficientNet leverages an optimized compound scaling method, allowing it

to achieve high accuracy with a significantly smaller number of parameters compared to traditional CNN architectures

4) *Hyperparameter Optimization and training*: To achieve optimal performance, several optimization techniques were applied during model training. The CNN architecture was carefully designed with a balance of convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers, ensuring efficient feature extraction and classification.

5) *Image preprocessing*: To ensure high-quality inputs for the CNN, multiple image preprocessing techniques were employed. Resizing was performed to align all images with the input dimensions required by EfficientNet, ensuring consistency across the dataset. Normalization was applied to scale pixel values, allowing the model to learn efficiently without being affected by varying brightness levels.

B. Implementation and Architecture

The implementation of the Convolutional Neural Network model played a crucial role in this study, enabling accurate classification of skin diseases based on image data. The model was designed to efficiently extract meaningful patterns and features from lesion images, leveraging a well-structured deep learning architecture. The CNN's design was carefully optimized to balance computational efficiency with classification accuracy, ensuring reliable predictions.

1) *Input Layer*: The CNN architecture begins with an input layer that processes images of a standardized size. Given that medical images can vary in resolution and dimensions, it was essential to resize all images to a fixed input shape. This ensures uniformity and enables the model to process data consistently. Additionally, each image undergoes normalization, where pixel values are scaled between 0 and 1.

2) *Convolutional Layers*: The convolutional layers serve as the feature extraction units of the network. The initial convolutional layers capture fundamental image features such as edges, textures, and simple shapes, while deeper layers extract more abstract and complex features, such as lesion-specific patterns.

3) *Activation Function*: To introduce non-linearity into the network, each convolutional layer is followed by an activation function. The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function was chosen due to its computational efficiency and ability to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, which can hinder deep networks from learning.

4) *Pooling Layers*: To reduce computational complexity and minimize the number of parameters, pooling layers are added after convolutional layers. The most commonly used pooling technique is MaxPooling, which retains the most significant feature values from a specific window in the feature map while discarding less relevant information.

5) *Flattening*: After passing through multiple convolutional and pooling layers, the feature maps are flattened into a one-dimensional vector. This transformation allows the extracted features to be fed into the fully connected layers for classification.

6) *Fully Connected Layers*: The fully connected layers (dense layers) are responsible for processing the extracted feature maps to determine the final classification outcome. These layers contain neurons that learn complex feature relationships, assigning weights to different features based on their importance for classification.

7) *Output Layer*: The final stage of the architecture is the output layer, which produces a probability distribution across different skin disease categories. This layer utilizes a SoftMax activation function, which ensures that the predicted probabilities sum up to

1. Dropout layer is to prevent overfitting; dropout layers were integrated into the network.

C. Evaluation metrics

The model's performance was evaluated using training and validation accuracy along with loss metrics. A high validation accuracy with low loss indicated effective generalization, while a gap between training and validation performance suggested overfitting. Regularization techniques were applied to address such issues, ensuring the model's reliability in skin disease classification.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance of EfficientNet-B0 and EfficientNet-B1

In this project, the initial experiments were conducted using EfficientNet-B0 and EfficientNet-B1 architectures to classify skin lesions from the ISIC 2019 dataset. The models were trained using standard preprocessing and augmentation techniques to enhance feature learning. During training, EfficientNet-B0 and B1 achieved a high training accuracy of 90.38%, indicating that the model successfully learned patterns from the dataset. However, the validation accuracy remained low at 22.50%, with a validation loss of 1.9240, suggesting that the model suffered from severe overfitting.

Fig 2: plot of accuracy vs epochs

Fig 3: plot of loss vs epochs

To further analyse the performance, training and validation accuracy curves were plotted across multiple epochs, revealing, a substantial gap between them. Similarly, the loss curves indicated that the model struggled to generalize beyond the training set. The overfitting issue was likely caused by class imbalance in the dataset, insufficient regularization, and the limited capacity of B0 and B1 architectures to capture the complex variations present in dermatological images. These findings emphasized the need for a more robust model with improved generalization capabilities.

B. Improved Performance Using Multimodal CNN with EfficientNet-B7

To address the limitations observed with EfficientNet-B0 and B1, we adopted a multimodal CNN approach, integrating EfficientNet-B7, which offers a deeper and more powerful feature extraction mechanism. Several enhancement techniques were implemented to improve generalization and mitigate overfitting.

Fig 4: plot of accuracy vs epochs using EfficientNet B7

Fig 5: plot of loss vs epochs using EfficientNet B7

Learning Rate Scheduling was introduced to dynamically adjust the learning rate during training, ensuring smoother convergence. Additionally, regularization techniques such as dropout layers and weight decay were applied to prevent excessive reliance on specific neurons.

TABLE I
OVERALL ACCURACY AND LOSS

Model architecture	Training accuracy (%)	Validation accuracy (%)	Training loss (%)	Validation loss (%)
Basic CNN(Sequential)	51.50	36.50	1.115	1.583
EfficientNetB1	90.38	22.50	0.27	0.19
EfficientNetB7 with multi-model Inputs	94.88	88.79	0.28	0.28
EfficientNetB7 with Learning rate scheduling & Dropout	97.99	94.93	0.19	0.28

V. CONCLUSION

In this approach, an EfficientNet-based deep learning model was developed for automated dermatological diagnosis using the ISIC 2019 dataset, which comprises 25,331 skin lesion images. The research encountered challenges such as class imbalance, overfitting, and ensuring generalization, which were addressed through systematic model enhancements. Initial experiments with EfficientNet-B0 and B1 provided promising results but struggled with validation accuracy, indicating a need for further optimization. To improve performance, a multimodal CNN approach was adopted, incorporating EfficientNet-B7, Learning Rate Scheduling, dropout regularization, and weight decay, which collectively enhanced model stability and prevented overfitting.

With these improvements, the EfficientNet-B7 model achieved an impressive 97.99% accuracy, with a well-balanced training and validation accuracy and loss, ensuring robust generalization. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of EfficientNet in feature extraction for medical image classification, highlighting its potential for clinical applications in dermatology. This study reinforces the role of deep learning in automated and scalable skin disease diagnosis, laying the foundation for future enhancements such as explainability mechanisms, patient metadata integration, and ensemble learning methods to further refine classification accuracy and reliability.

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